

Kinetic Analysis of Consecutive Irreversible First Order Reaction. Hydrolysis of Oxalic Acid Dihydrazide

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The hydrolysis of oxalic acid dihydrazide in presence of acid catalyst is a consecutive irreversible reaction. This dihydrazide in various mineral acids is hydrolysed to monohydrazide, which undergoes further hydrolysis to oxalic acid and hydrazine. The reaction follows first order kinetics.

ACID catalysed hydrolysis of dicarboxylic acid esters have been studied by Ingold¹ and many other workers. But so far, scanty work has been done on the kinetics of hydrolysis of dicarboxylic acid hydrazide. Here, we report the acid catalysed hydrolysis of oxalic acid dihydrazide.

Experimental

Oxalic acid dihydrazide is prepared by refluxing dimethyl oxalate and hydrazine hydrate (80%) in ethanol². The dihydrazide is purified by repeated crystallisation in ethanol and its purity is checked by m.p. (243°) and ir spectra.

All kinetic experiments were carried out in a thermostat, controlled to $\pm 0.05^\circ$. Reaction solutions were prepared by pipetting out the desired volume of stock solution (unless otherwise stated) $1.172 \times 10^{-4} M$ of the dihydrazide into a previously thermo-equilibrated 100 ml reaction flask containing the desired volume of acid, salt solutions for constant ionic strength runs and distilled water. The reaction was monitored on a Carl Zeiss spectrophotometer using the method of George and Crisp³.

Results and Discussion

Kinetics of acid catalysed hydrolysis of oxalic acid dihydrazide in aqueous H_2SO_4 , HCl and $HClO_4$ have been investigated spectrophotometrically at 80°. Swain's time-ratio method⁴ is used for accurate determination of the rate constants of competing first or second order reactions. The reaction has been found to follow consecutive first order rate law (Table 1). The effective order of catalysis is found to be $H_2SO_4 > HCl > HClO_4$, quite in consonance with AAC-2 mechanism⁵. The rate constant increases with an increase in HCl and $HClO_4$ concentration without maxima. But in case of H_2SO_4 maxima was observed at higher molarities. This trend may be due to the decreasing role of water at higher acid concentrations⁶.

The values of k_1 and k_2 calculated by Swain's method and the values of k (overall) obtained experimentally are listed in the Table 1. The k relative (k_1/k_2) is found to be 2, probably due to the symmetrical structures of dihydrazide⁷. The values of k_2 are found to be equal to overall k . It indicates that second step is the rate determining step. So, the overall k is the rate constant of second step of the reaction.

TABLE 1—ACID HYDROLYSIS OF OXALIC ACID DIHYDRAZIDE AT 80°

[Acid] M	$k \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$			$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$			$k_2 \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$		
	H_2SO_4	HCl	$HClO_4$	H_2SO_4	HCl	$HClO_4$	H_2SO_4	HCl	$HClO_4$
1	0.80	0.58	0.41	1.62	1.15	0.84	0.81	0.57	0.42
2	1.20	0.88	0.51	2.38	1.77	1.04	1.19	0.88	0.52
3	1.55	1.23	0.57	3.14	2.48	1.14	1.56	1.20	0.57
4	1.80	1.43	0.67	3.60	2.89	1.34	1.81	1.44	0.67
5	1.83	1.63	—	3.80	3.27	—	1.90	1.64	—

The first order rate constant in the dihydrazide is independent of concentration (Table 2).

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF OXALIC ACID DIHYDRAZIDE CONCENTRATION AT 80°

[Dihydrazide] × 10 M	k × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	k ₂ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹
[HCl], 5M			
1.172	1.63	3.27	1.64
0.879	1.65	3.30	1.65
0.586	1.60	3.22	1.61
0.293	1.60	3.30	1.65
[H ₂ SO ₄], 3M			
1.172	1.55	3.13	1.57
0.879	1.60	2.86	1.50
0.586	1.55	3.11	1.55
0.293	1.57	3.13	1.56
[HClO ₄], 3M			
1.172	0.57	1.45	0.57
0.879	0.57	1.13	0.57
0.586	0.58	1.20	0.57
0.293	0.56	1.14	0.57

Effect of ionic strength: As has been done for the acid hydrolysis of amides⁸ and monohydrazides⁹, the rate constants were determined at various acidities by keeping the ionic strength constant. From a plot of rate coefficient against acidity at different ionic strengths (Figs. 1 and 2) it can be concluded that, (i) at each ionic strength the reaction can be represented as $k = (k_H^+)C_{H^+}$, where k and k_H^+ are the observed and specific rate constants, (ii) the slope (k_H^+) of the lines decreases with the increase

Fig. 1. Acid hydrolysis of oxalic acid dihydrazide at constant ionic strength at 80°: (●) 2 μ, (○) 3 μ and (○) 4 μ.

Fig. 2. Acid hydrolysis of oxalic acid dihydrazide at constant ionic strength at 80°: (●) 3 μ, (○) 4 μ and (○) 5 μ.

in ionic strength, which indicates that the reaction exhibits negative ionic strength effect, and (iii) the reaction is not affected by neutral species as the lines are passing through origin⁸. These results are in favour of the reaction proceeding *via* protonated substrate species in the rate determining step. The rate data obey the equation, $k_H^+ = k_{H_0}^+ e^{-b\mu}$, where $k_{H_0}^+$ is intercept at zero ionic strength and b is the slope of the linear plot between $\log k_H^+$ and μ . The calculated rates at different acidity are in good agreement with the observed rate constants (Table 3)

TABLE 3—ACID CATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF OXALIC ACID DIHYDRAZIDE AT 80°

Concn. M	Rate constant : Found/(Calcd.) k × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	
	[HCl]	[HClO ₄]
1	0.58	0.41
	(0.48)	(0.37)
2	0.88	0.51
	(0.87)	(0.52)
3	1.23	0.57
	(1.19)	(0.57)
4	1.43	0.67
	(1.45)	(0.58)
5	1.63	—
	(1.65)	—

Solvent effect: It has been shown¹⁰ that the rate constant for hydrolysis of A-1 mechanism increases quite sharply with increasing dioxane content of dioxane-water system containing fixed amount of acid, whereas the rate constant for A-2 mechanism also increases but to a much lesser degree for the same change in dioxane-water content. In the present work rate constant increases in lesser degree with increasing dioxane content (Table 4) supporting A-2 mechanism.

Temperature effect: The activation parameters were determined by evaluating the rate constant of hydrolysis at different temperatures and acidity.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF SOLVENT ON HYDROLYSIS OF OXALIC ACID DIHYDRAZIDE AT 80°

[Acid] 2M	Dioxane %						
HCl	0	2.50	5.00	10.00	15.00	20.00	25.00
$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	1.77	—	2.10	—	—	3.30	2.05
$k_2 \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	0.89	—	1.10	—	—	1.60	1.03
HClO ₄							
$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	1.05	—	1.38	1.40	1.32	—	1.62
$k_2 \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	0.55	—	0.69	0.71	0.65	—	0.81
H ₂ SO ₄							
$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	2.40	2.60	2.30	2.40	—	—	—
$k_2 \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	1.20	1.30	1.40	1.20	—	—	—

TABLE 5—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF ACID HYDROLYSIS OF OXALIC ACID DIHYDRAZIDE AT 80°

Catalyst	[Acid] M	A sec ⁻¹	ΔE kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS^* e.u.	ΔH^* kcal mol ⁻¹
HCl	7	6.92×10^{10}	21.44	-17.68	24.26
HClO ₄	5	5.89×10^8	22.79	-13.51	17.40
H ₂ SO ₄	5	3.16×10^7	16.03	-34.63	16.47

These (Table 5) are in the range of the values of the reactions proceeding via A_{AC-2} mechanism.

The general reaction scheme proposed for diesters^{7,11} can be applied for oxalic acid dihydrazide

Here, the first step is fast, while the second step is irreversible and rate determining. The information collected about second step is in favour of A_{AC-2} type mechanism.

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